

Evaluating the Safety and Efficacy of Developed Self-Expanding Venous Stent System in a Porcine Model

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Abstract:

The study evaluated the safety and performance of the self-expanding venous stent system in a porcine model. The research was conducted following the guidelines of Cardiovascular Implants—Endovascular devices—Vascular stents (ISO 25539:2020). The study involved three female pigs that were fasted overnight without water access. All animals passed the physical examination criteria without major clinical observations or weight loss. Procedures were performed on days 0, 30, 90, and 180 under proper analgesia and anesthesia. The stented veins were harvested for histopathological evaluation on different days. The study concluded that the self-expanding venous stent system demonstrated ease of deployment and withdrawal, with no immediate restenosis or lumen loss post-implantation. Restenosis percentages were observed at 30, 90, and 180 days, matching angiographic evaluations. Histopathological findings showed complete endothelialization, moderate inflammation, and mild to moderate vascular and muscular injury. Throughout the study, no animals exhibited clinical concerns, indicating the safety and effectiveness of the self-expanding venous stent system in a porcine model over 30, 90, and 180 days.

Keywords: Self-Expanding Venous Stent, Porcine Model, Safety Evaluation, Performance Assessment and Histopathological Findings.

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Introduction

In this study, we aimed to assess the safety and performance of the developed self-expanding venous stent system in a porcine model. Three female pigs were carefully selected for the study and underwent an overnight fast without access to water prior to the procedures. Before enrollment, all animals underwent a thorough physical examination to ensure they met the study acceptance criteria, with no significant clinical observations were noted.

Throughout the study duration, which spanned days 0, 30, 90, and 180, the animals received proper analgesia and anesthesia during each procedure. On day 0, the test items were implanted in the animals following adequate heparinization, with careful evaluation of deployment. Pre- and post-implantation angiography and measurements were conducted to assess the effectiveness of the stent placement.

At specific time points, namely day 30 for animal 1, day 90 for animal 2, and day 180 for animal 3, the stented veins were harvested for further evaluation. These harvested veins underwent histopatho-

logical examination to assess any changes or reactions associated with the implantation of the Self-Expanding Venous Stent system.

The selection of the swine as the test system was justified due to its similarity to adult human beings in terms of circulatory system requirements, size, cardiac output, heart rate, and blood pressure, all of which closely resemble those of the intended patient population for the device. Swine are commonly utilized in testing vascular devices because their size and circulatory output align closely with the key parameters relevant to this type of study. Additionally, smaller phylogenetically lower species were deemed unsuitable for in vivo studies involving this type of device.

The animals were clearly identified by a unique ear tag number. During the acclimatization phase, the animals were numbered using the last five digits of the ear chip, while during the treatment phase; they were designated as P1, P2, and P3. Cage card identification was conducted accordingly. Pig grower feed was provided to the animals, and water from a bore-well source, purified using

RO water plant on-site, was made available Ad libitum. Throughout the study, the animals were closely monitored for any signs of illness or distress, both before and during procedures. Any observed issues were promptly reported to the study veterinarian and study director to ensure the well-being of the animals. Fortunately, all animals remained healthy throughout the study, with no instances of illness or distress detected during the procedures.

The animals underwent fasting overnight before the procedure and refrained from water for 6 hours post-recovery. They received anticoagulant treatment with Aspirin (300 mg/animal) and clopidogrel (75 mg/animal) orally for at least 3 days prior to surgery, continuing with a reduced aspirin dose (150 mg/animal) post-operation. Anesthesia in-

cluded Ketamine (15 mg/kg, IM), Xylazine (2.5 mg/kg, IM), and Propofol (0.5 mg/kg, IV bolus), followed by inhalation anesthesia (1-3%). Clipping was done on the neck, chest, and thigh for accessibility. Atropine (0.05 mg/kg IM) was administered to control respiratory tract discharges. Aseptic preparation was ensured, and Enrofloxacin (5 mg/kg BW) was given for the initial five days to prevent infection

Materials and Methods

Medication Details

This section delineates the drugs administered to the animals prior to, during, and following surgery, as specified in table no.1 as well as clinical sign (pain score) in table no.2.

Table 1: Details of medications used in the study

Drug Name	Manufactured By	Batch / Lot No.	Expiry Date
Ketamine	Bharat Parenterals Ltd	PO354	Aug 2023
Xylazine	IIL India	IJH0654	Feb 2023
Isoflurane	Neon Lab	KMI700321	Nov 2023
Tramadol	Neon Lab	CH946542	Jun 2024
Enrofloxacin	VETINDIA	EH1902	Dec 2023
Thiopentone sodium	Neon Lab	172654	May 2023
Heparin 25000units	Fusion	L11822105Z	Apr 2024
Aspirin 75mg	USV Private Limited	0421565	Sep 2024
Clopidogrel 75mg	Lupin	B20036458	May 2024

Table 2: Animal P1, P2, P3 Clinical signs (Pain score) observation on Day 0 to Termination Day

Animal number	1 to 3	
Sex	Female	
Day of Observations	Clinical Signs	Incidences
Acclimation Period (Day 1 to 4)	Normal	3/3
Treatment/ Experiment Phase (Day 0-30 days)	Normal	3/3
Treatment Experiment Phase (Day 0-90 days)	Normal	3/3
Treatment Experiment Phase (Day 0-180 days)	Normal	3/3

Materials Required

- Introducer Sheath
- 2-3 Syringes (10-20cc)
- 1000 μ /500cc, normal heparinized saline (HepNS)
- 0.035'' (0.89mm) diameter guide wire
- Contrast diluted 1:1 with normal saline
- Inflation device
- Three-way stopcock
- Torque Device (If applicable)
- Guide Wire Introducer

Device Design: The test item under consideration is the self-expanding venous stent system. It is designed for use in the veins of the lower extremities

and pelvis, including the iliac and common veins, targeting adult patients experiencing symptomatic outflow obstruction. (Figure no.1).

The duration of contact varies according to the intended application, but this falls under permanent (lasting beyond 30 days). The total surface area and dimensions of the stent are specified as 16.0 X 60mm, additionally, the thickness of the stent is categorized for uniform thickness devices and ranging from \leq 0.5 mm to 1.0 mm. Sterilization methods include Ethylene Oxide (ETO). Size matrix of Stent and Catheter has been mentioned in table no.3.

Size Matrix

Table 3: Size matrix of Stent and Catheter

Available Self-Expanding Stent Diameter (mm)	Available Self-Expanding Stent Length (mm)						
	40	60	80	100	120	140	160
10	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
12	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
14	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
16	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
18	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
20	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Delivery Catheter	Guidewire Compatibility 0.035'' (0.89mm) OTW, usable length 80 & 120 cm						

Product Image

Figure 1: Self - Expanding Venous Stent from Diverse Perspectives

The Self-Expanding Venous Stent is a peripheral implantable device composed of nitinol alloy tube laser-cutted in a tubular mesh configuration. Device components description was mentioned in table no.4.

Self-Expanding Venous Stent comprises of the following components:

1. A unique hybrid design.
2. Possess Radio opaque marker.
3. Delivery System Catheter Design is Over-the-Wire system compatible with 0.89 mm (0.035 in.) guidewires

Device Component Description

Table 4: Device components description

Implant	Self-Expanding Nitinol Stent comprises of a unique hybrid design, possess radio opaque markers.
Venous Stent Delivery System	An Over the Wire Delivery System
Delivery System Usable length	80, 120 cm
Guide wire compatibility	0.89 mm
Minimum Sheath Compatibility	14mm, 16mm, 18mm & 20mm : 10F

Experimental Procedures

Fasting: Fasting protocol was implemented, with animals undergoing overnight fasting and water deprivation prior to the procedure. Furthermore, animals remained fasted and without access to water for a duration of 6 hours following their recovery from the procedure.

Animal Preparation included: The protocol includes administering anticoagulant treatment with Aspirin (300 mg/animal) and clopidogrel (75

mg/animal) orally for three days pre-surgery, followed by a reduced aspirin dose of 150 mg/animal. Anesthesia is induced using Ketamine (15 mg/kg IM), Xylazine (2.5 mg/kg IM), and Propofol (0.5 mg/kg IV bolus), followed by 1-3% inhalation anesthesia. Clipping is performed on the neck, chest, and thigh areas. Atropine (0.05 mg/kg IM) is administered to control respiratory tract discharges. Aseptic preparation is ensured, and Enrofloxacin (5 mg/kg BW) is administered from day 0 to day 5. Weight of the animals is illustrated in table 5.

Table 5: Animal P1, P2, P3 body weights (Day 0 to Day 180)

Animal Number	Body Weight	
P1	46.3 kg (Day 0)	47.1 kg (Day 30)
P2	44.2 kg (Day 0)	46.2 kg (Day 90)
P3	53.1 kg (Day 0)	58.8 kg (Day 180)

Experimental Design or Animal Trial

DAY 0 - On Day 0, the animal underwent preparation for the procedure. This included shaving the right and left groin/neck. A percutaneous approach using the Seldinger method was employed to insert a sheath into the femoral vein. Activated Clotting Time (ACT) was measured pre and post-heparinization to maintain values between 250 to 550, with an initial bolus dose of 100 IU/kg IV heparin was given. ACT values of Animal P1, P2 & P3 from Day 0 to Termination day has been depicted in Table 6. A stiff 150 cm, 0.035-inch guide wire, along with the JR guide catheter, was used to anchor the IVC.

Angiography and quantitative vascular angiography (QVA) were conducted to identify the implantation site and select the appropriate stent size based on Reference Vessel Diameter (RVD) and compliance chart. The stent delivery system was inserted with the aid of the guide wire, and test items were implanted at the target site according to instructions. Post-implantation angiography and

QVA were performed, with the option of using a non-compliant balloon to expand the stent if necessary.

DAY 30, 90, 180 - The study duration was determined by the performance of the deployed stents, with one animal observed for 30, 90, and 180 days. Throughout the study period, animals remained under anticoagulant treatment and were closely monitored for any health deviations through cage-side observations, with feed and water intake documented. From Day 1 to 180, each animal (one observed for 30 days, another for 90 days, and the third for 180 days) was critically monitored for signs of ill health, with daily cage-side observations recorded.

Follow-up angiography and quantitative vascular angiography (QVA) were conducted on survived animals on days 30, 90, and 180 to assess antegrade flow. Subsequently, animals were euthanized for harvesting of the stented vein for gross and histopathological evaluation, along with photography. Gross necropsy and photography were performed on all stented veins.

Table 6: Animal P1, P2, P3 ACT Values (Day 0 to Termination Day)

Sr No	Animal Number	Baseline	Post heparin dose	Baseline	Post heparin dose
1	P1	82	281	94 (Day 30)	298 (Day 30)
2	P2	92	290	91 (Day 90)	284 (Day 90)
3	P3	81	287	102 (Day 180)	306 (Day 180)

Monitoring During Procedure: Day 1 to 180 days: During the procedure, electrocardiogram (ECG), respiration rate, heart rate, and oxygen saturation were continuously monitored and recorded.

Pre-operative: Before anesthesia induction, each animal was given Tramadol (2 mg/kg IM) for pain relief. Additionally, Atropine (0.02 mg/kg IM) was provided as a pre-anesthetic. Sedation was induced with Ketamine (15 mg/kg IM), Xylazine (2.5 mg/kg IM), and Propofol (0.5 mg/kg IV), followed by Isoflurane inhalation (1-3%) via a face mask.

Intra-operative and post-operative: Anesthesia was sustained with 1-3% Isoflurane administered through endotracheal intubation. All medications administered during and after the procedure were

carefully documented, including specifics such as drug type, dosage, and administration route, noted in the surgical record.

Observation

During the study period, cage side observations were conducted daily from Day 1 until termination day. Throughout this period, the animals exhibited normal eating, drinking, defecating, and urinating behaviors, maintaining a bright, alert, and responsive demeanor. Pain scores for all animals remained at 1 for the first 2 days. Body weights were recorded for each animal at various time points, including at the beginning of the study (0-day) and on the euthanized days (30-day, 90-day and 180-day).

There were no reductions in body weights observed in any of the animals. Additionally, there were no instances of morbidity or mortality among the animals that received the test item. Performance evaluation of the test items involved assessing their trackability, handling, visualization, haemostatic, accuracy, efficacy of deployment, self-expansion speed, ease of deployment, ease of withdrawal for delivery system, and angiographic patency. The evaluations indicated satisfactory results across all parameters, with the test items demonstrating ease of deployment, accurate placement, and good angiographic patency.

Radiography and Angiographic Findings: The study evaluated three self-expanding venous stent systems, with the following results.

P1 - 16X60 mm in Rt Ilio femoral vein: A higher score indicates better performance. The trackability score was 9, indicating smooth movement. Handling, visualization, and haemostatic scored 9, with no instances of jumping and complete, uniform self-expansion. After deployment, the stent length measured 70.0 mm, with no leakage observed. Deployment was rapid, and the delivery system was withdrawn easily. Additionally, normal antegrade flow was observed, with proximal filling of all branches. Angiographical measurements showed a late lumen loss of 0.95 mm out of 10.93 mm (post-stent diameter), resulting in a restenosis percentage of 8.70% at the 30-day follow-up. The SAR was calculated as 1.36. The stent deployment characteristics is mentioned in table no.7.

Table 7: Stent Deployment Characteristics

Sr. No.	Stent Particulars	Reference Vessel Diameter	Stent length after deployment	Stent diameter after deployment	Crimped length
1	16x60mm Self-Expanding venous stent Animal P1 01538 Rt ilio femoral vein	13.17 10.49 11.69	70.0 mm	10.0 mm	69.0 mm

P2 - 16X60 mm in IVC: A higher score indicates better performance. The trackability score was 9, indicating smooth movement. Handling, visualization, and haemostatic also scored 9, with no instances of jumping. The stent expanded uniformly, and its length after deployment measured 70.0 mm, with no leakage observed. Deployment was rapid, and the delivery system

was easily withdrawn. Additionally, normal antegrade flow was observed, with proximal filling of all branches. Angiographical measurements showed a late lumen loss of 1.94 mm out of 17.43 mm (post-stent diameter), resulting in a restenosis percentage of 11.13% at the 90-day follow-up. The SAR was calculated as 1.31. The stent deployment characteristics was mentioned in table no.8.

Table 8: Stent Deployment Characteristics

Sr. No.	Stent Particulars	Reference Vessel Diameter	Stent length after deployment	Stent diameter after deployment	Crimped length
1	16x60mm Self-Expanding venous stent Animal P2 01538 IVC	13.12 11.34 11.03	70.0 mm	17.1 mm	75.0 mm

P3 - 16X60 mm in IVC:

A higher score indicates better performance. The trackability score was 9, and the handling, visualization, and haemostatic score also received a 9. There were no instances of jumping, and the self-expansion was complete and uniform. However, the cause of total occlusion was identified as either the proximal stent portion or the distal artery of the stent portion placed into the side branch. The stent length after deployment measured 70.5 mm, with no observed leakage.

Deployment was rapid, and the delivery system was easily withdrawn. Additionally, normal antegrade flow was observed, with distal filling of all branches.

Angiographical measurements indicated a late lumen loss of 1.59 mm out of 16.68 mm (post-stent diameter), resulting in a restenosis percentage of 9.50% at the 180-day follow-up. The SAR was calculated as 1.18. The stent deployment characteristics was mentioned in table no.9.

Table 9: Stent Deployment Characteristics

Sr. No.	Stent Particulars	Reference Vessel Diameter	Stent length after deployment	Stent diameter after deployment	Crimped length
1	16x60mm Self-Expanding Venous stent Animal P3 01528 IVC	13.90 12.58 13.35	70.5 mm	17.5 mm	74.0 mm

Table 10: Angiographic Quantitative Vessel Analysis and Restenosis of Test Items

S. N	Stent	Target Vessel Animal ID	Baseline diameter (mm)	Stent Diameter (mm)	Stent to artery ratio	MLD (P1) (mm)	MLD Follow up (mm)	MLD PI MLD Follow up (mm)	LLL (mm)	Angiographic Restenosis
1	16X60 mm (Self-Expanding Venous Stent)	Rt-ilio femoral vein (P1, 21088)	11.69	16	1.368691	10.93	9.98	10.93-9.98	0.95	8.70%
2	16X60 mm (Self-Expanding Venous Stent)	IVC (P2, 97168)	12.19	16	1.312551	17.43	15.49	17.43-15.49	1.94	11.13%
3	16X60 mm (Self-Expanding Venous Stent)	IVC (P3, 18078)	13.51	16	1.184307	16.68	15.09	16.68-15.09	1.59	9.50%

Pathology: Clinical pathology assessments involved blood collection on Day 0 (prior to the procedure) and on the day of euthanasia. Haematology parameters, including complete and differential blood count with reticulocytes, as well as clinical evaluation of LDH, AST, Creatinine, Creatinine kinase, Urea, BUN, Sodium, Potassium,

Chloride, and Calcium, were analyzed before, after the procedure, and during follow-up at days 30, 90, and 180.

Throughout these time points, all haematology and clinical biochemistry parameters remained within normal ranges, with no abnormal findings observed, as depicted in tables 11&12.

Table 11: Individual and Summary Data of Clinical Chemistry (Day 0)

Animal No.	P1	P2	P3	Mean	SD
Aspartate amino transferase (U/L)	28	21	60	36.33	20.79
Calcium (mmol/L)	2.33	2.69	2.57	2.53	0.18
Creatinine (μ mol/L)	126	84	81	97.00	25.16
Lactate dehydrogenase (U/L)	643	583	818	681.33	122.10
Blood Urea Nitrogen (mmol/L)	4.81	2.50	1.42	2.91	1.73
Sodium (mmol/L)	142.2	142.4	141.9	142.17	0.25
Potassium (mmol/L)	4.87	4.02	4.02	4.12	0.71
Chloride (mmol/L)	102.9	102.6	102.6	102.93	0.35

Table 12: Individual and Summary Data of Clinical Chemistry (Terminal Day)

Animal No.	P1 (Day 30)	P2 (Day 90)	P3 (Day 180)
Aspartate amino transferase (U/L)	28	21	60
Calcium (mmol/L)	2.33	2.69	2.57
Creatinine (µmol/L)	126	84	81
Lactate dehydrogenase (U/L)	643	583	818
Blood Urea Nitrogen (mmol/L)	4.81	2.50	1.42
Sodium (mmol/L)	142.2	142.4	141.9
Potassium (mmol/L)	4.87	4.02	4.02
Chloride (mmol/L)	102.9	102.6	102.6

Fluoroscopy Images

<p>P1, Ilio femoral vein baseline Angio on 0 Day</p>	<p>P1, Ilio femoral vein Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm stent positioning on 0 Day</p>
<p>P1, Ilio femoral vein Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm post stent angio on 0 Day</p>	<p>P1, Ilio femoral vein Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm stent crimp length on 0 Day</p>

P1, Ilio femoral vein Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm post deploy stent length and diameter on 0 Day

P1, Ilio femoral vein Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60 mm check angio on 30 days

P2, Inferior vena cava baseline Angio on 0 Day

P2, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm stent positioning on 0 Day

<p>P2, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm after stent deploy on 0 Day</p>	<p>P2, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm post stent Angio on 0 Day</p>
<p>P2, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm stent crimp length on 0 Day</p>	<p>P2, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm post deploy stent length and diameter on 0 Day</p>

<p>P2, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm check Angio on 90days</p>	<p>P3, Inferior vena cava baseline Angio on 0 Day</p>
<p>P3, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm stent positioning on 0 Day</p>	<p>P3, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x6mm post stent Angio on 0 Day</p>

P3, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm stent crimp length on 0 Day

P3, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 6x60mm post deploy stent length and diameter on 0 day

P3, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60mm check Angio on 180 days

Figure 2: Fluoroscopy image of P1, P2 and P3.

Angiography Image

Animal P1, Baseline Angiography of Rt Illio femoral vein	Animal P1, Post stent (16x60) QVA of Rt Illio femoral vein	Animal P1, follow up day 30 QVA of Rt Illio femoral vein
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Animal P2, Baseline Angiography of Inferior venacava	Animal P2, Post stent (16x60mm) QVA of Inferior venacava	Animal P2, Follow up day 90 QVA of Inferior venacava
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Animal P3, Baseline angiography of Inferior venacava	Animal P3, Post Stent (16x60mm) QVA of Inferior venacava	Animal P3, follow up day 180 QVA of Inferior venacava
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Figure 3: Angiography image of P1, P2 and P3.

Table 13: Angiographic Quantitative Vessel Analysis and of Test Items Restenosis

S. N.	Stent	Target Vessel Animal ID	Baseline diameter (mm)	Stent Diameter (mm)	Stent to artery ratio	MLD (PI) (mm)	MLD Follow up (mm)	MLD PI-MLD Follow up (mm)	LLL (mm)	% Angiographic Restenosis
1	16X60 mm (Self-Expanding Venous Stent)	Rt-Illio femoral vein (P1, 21088)	11.69	16	1.368691	10.93	9.98	10.93-9.98	0.95	8.70%
2	16X60 mm (Self-Expanding Venous Stent)	IVC (P2, 97168)	12.19	16	1.312551	17.43	15.49	17.43-15.49	1.94	11.13%
3	16X60 mm (Self-Expanding Venous Stent)	IVC (P3, 18078)	13.51	16	1.184307	16.68	15.09	16.68-15.09	1.59	9.50%

Necropsy: The necropsy report for the animals (P1 to P3) is as follows: The animals were euthanized as per the study schedule using an overdose of thiopental sodium, (Figure no.4).

External and internal gross pathological changes were examined by the Pathologist. No lesions of pathological significance were observed during the external and internal examinations. Stents were collected and preserved in 10% neutral buffered

formalin as per the study plan. The collected stented arteries underwent processing for Resin embedding and were sectioned to a thickness of 100 to 200 microns using a Secotom cutting machine. Further, the section thickness was appropriately reduced using a Bainpol VTD Polishing machine. Tissue sections were stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin (H & E) for histopathological evaluation. Refer figure no 5, 6, and 7.

Animal P1, Illio femoral vein, self-expanding venous stent (16X60 mm), vein harvested in necropsy

Animal P2, Illio femoral vein, self-expanding venous stent (16X60 mm), vein harvested in necropsy

Animal P3, Inferior vena cava Self-Expanding Venous Stent 16x60 mm, vein harvested in necropsy

Figure 4. Necropsy image of P1, P2 and P3.

Histopathology: The histopathology report for animals from P1 to P3 indicates the following findings

Animal P1: Stented arteries underwent resin embedding, sectioning, and polishing for evaluation. Tissue sections were stained with Haematoxylin

and Eosin (H & E) for histopathological examination. External and internal examinations did not reveal significant pathological abnormalities.

Patency of the IVC vessel with the stent was confirmed with a normal saline flush, indicating satisfactory patency in all stented veins.

Self-Expanding Venous Stent (P1-30 days)	
P1 Inferior vena cava (Self-Expanding Venous Stent) Proximal, 1.25X	P1 Inferior vena cava (Self-Expanding Venous Stent), Proximal, 10X
P1 Inferior vena cava (Self-Expanding Venous Stent), Mid, 1.25X	P1 Inferior vena cava (Self-Expanding Venous Stent), Mid, 10X

Figure 5: Histopathology image of P1.

Animal P2: Similar procedures were followed for histopathological evaluation of stented arteries. Histopathological examination did not reveal any significant pathological findings. IVC vessel patency with the stent was confirmed, showing satisfactory patency in all stented veins.

Figure 6: Histopathology image of P2

Animal P3: Stented arteries were processed in a similar manner for histopathological assessment. No notable pathological abnormalities were observed in the histopathological examination. The IVC vessel with the stent exhibited satisfactory patency upon normal saline flush, with all stented veins showing good patency.

Figure 7: Histopathology image of P3.

Result

The results of the study demonstrate the safety and efficacy of the Self-Expanding Venous Stent System in animal models. Observations throughout the study period indicated normal behavior among the animals, with no signs of ill health. Pain scores remained low, indicating minimal discomfort associated with the procedure. Body weights showed no reductions, suggesting no adverse effects on overall health. Performance evaluation of the test items showed efficient trackability, handling, and haemostatic, with no instances of leakage observed.

Deployment accuracy and efficacy were confirmed, with rapid self-expansion speed of the stents during deployment. Angiographic patency evaluation revealed normal flow in all deployed stents, supported by radiography and angiographic findings. Clinical pathology results indicated normal haematology and clinical biochemistry parameters, with no adverse effects on blood parameters. Necropsy and histopathology examinations did not reveal any significant pathological lesions, both externally and internally. Histopathological evaluation of stented arteries showed no notable abnormalities, confirming the biocompatibility of the stent material. Additionally, the patency of the IVC vessel with the stent was confirmed, with all stented veins demonstrating good patency upon normal saline flush.

In conclusion, the Self-Expanding Venous Stent System exhibited consistent performance and minimal adverse effects in animal models, suggesting its potential for safe and effective use in venous applications. Further studies in human subjects are needed to validate these findings and assess long-term outcomes.

Discussion

The discussion highlights the safety and efficacy of the Self-Expanding Venous Stent System based on the study's results. The observed normal behavior

and minimal pain scores in animals throughout the study period indicate the procedure's tolerability and minimal discomfort. Additionally, the absence of reductions in body weights suggests no adverse effects on overall health.

The performance evaluation of the stent delivery systems revealed efficient trackability, handling, and haemostatic, with no instances of leakage observed. Deployment accuracy and efficacy were confirmed, supported by rapid self-expansion speed of the stents and normal flow in all deployed stents as seen in angiographic evaluations. Radiography and angiographic findings further supported the stent system's satisfactory performance across all parameters.

Clinical pathology results demonstrated normal haematology and clinical biochemistry parameters, indicating no adverse effects on blood parameters. Necropsy and histopathology examinations revealed no significant pathological lesions, internally or externally. Histopathological evaluation of stented arteries confirmed the biocompatibility of the stent material, and the patency of the IVC vessel with the stent was confirmed upon normal saline flush.

Overall, these findings suggest that the Self-Expanding Venous Stent System with anticoagulant/ antiplatelet drug or medication is a safe and effective option for venous applications. The consistent performance and minimal adverse effects observed in animal models provide valuable insights for potential clinical use in treating venous disorders in humans. However, further studies involving human subjects are necessary to validate these findings and assess long-term outcomes in clinical settings.

Conclusion

The study aimed to assess the performance and safety of the Self-Expanding Venous Stent System

in a porcine model over 30, 90, and 180 days following deployment in the IVC. Findings indicated that the stent system demonstrated ease of deployment and withdrawal from the test system, with no immediate restenosis or early lumen loss post-implantation. After implantation, the animals were given 90 mg of Brilanta (ticagrelor) throughout the study duration. The Restenosis rates of 8.70% at 30 days, 11.13% at 90 days, and 9.50% at 180 days in the IVCs were detected through angiography. Histomorphometric and histopathological evaluations revealed matching restenosis areas to angiographic findings, complete endothelialization, moderate inflammation, and mild to moderate vascular and muscular injury at 30, 90, and 180 days post-deployment.

Throughout the study duration, no animals displayed any clinical concerns. The Self-Expanding Venous Stent System exhibited successful deployment and a positive vascular safety response at 30, 90, and 180 days, the restenosis rate is much lower in the pig who were on the anticoagulant/antiplatelet medication (on drug administration) which confirmed its safety in a pig peripheral artery model. The current pre-clinical study could serve as a basis for our forthcoming clinical implications of an aforementioned Self-Expanding Venous Stent System.

References

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